

Propagation of Information Using Political Hashtags in Facebook: A Social Network Analysis

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Section 1: Introduction

Social media has become a powerful tool for spreading information, including political information. Hashtags are widely used on social media to categorize and share content. However, hashtags can also be used to spread information which may or may not be true. Political hashtags are particularly vulnerable to misuse, as they can be used to manipulate public opinion and influence political discourse (Committee on Intelligence, n.d.).

There is a growing body of research on the spread of misinformation and disinformation on social media. However, there is a limited understanding of how political hashtags are used to spread information on Facebook, the most popular social media platform in Sri Lanka (Kemp, 2023).

This study aims to understand how political hashtags are used to spread information on Facebook in Sri Lanka specifically with the use of Social Network Analysis (SNA). SNA approach elaborates about social networks where nodes represent people and edges represent the connection (Powell & Hopkins, 2015). Hence, the study seeks to answer the following research questions:

1. What are the large public groups and pages in Facebook that are publishing information (including political information) targeting

Sri Lanka during the time period of 1st of February, 2022 – 31st of August, 2022?

2. What are the prominent hashtags used on Facebook during the political unrest time period (1st of February, 2022 – 31st of August, 2022) in Sri Lanka?
3. What are the influential nodes in Facebook (verified and non-verified pages, public groups) that were involved in spreading posts with political hashtags during the political unrest period in Sri Lanka?

The existing literature on social media, Facebook hashtags, misinformation and disinformation, and social network analysis (SNA) provides a foundation for this study. Spread of misinformation will lead to issues related to trustworthiness, false amplification etc (Shu, et al., 2018). However, there is a lack of research specifically on the use of political hashtags on Facebook in Sri Lanka. This study aims to fill this gap by providing insights into how political hashtags are used to spread information on Facebook in Sri Lanka.

Section 2: Methodology

Type of Study

This study is primarily based on mixed method. Question 1 is answered using quantitative method, whereas question 2 is answered using qualitative approach and the third question is answered based on Social Network Analysis approach.

Population and Sample

The population of this study is all Facebook posts from Sri Lanka. The sample is a collection of 453 Facebook posts that were reshared from the “Ratta” Facebook page (StudioRatta, 2023), a popular political page in Sri Lanka, during the period of February 1st to August 31st, 2022.

Unit of Analysis

The unit of analysis for this research is considered as the Facebook posts with the political hashtags, which are posted by Sri Lankan public Facebook pages and groups.

Data Collection

The data for this study were collected from Facebook using Crowd Tangle (Brandon, 2023), a social media analytics tool.

Data Analysis

The data were analysed using Gephi (Gephi.org, 2023), a software package for social network analysis. Gephi was used to create a social network graph of the Facebook posts and their interactions. The graph was then analysed to identify the most popular political hashtags, the most influential nodes, and the dynamics of hashtag usage.

Time of Study

The data for this study were collected during the period of February 1st to August 31st, 2022. This period was selected because it was a time of high

political activity in Sri Lanka, with the country facing a number of economic and political challenges.

Section 3: Results and Discussion

The first research question involved identifying popular Facebook pages and groups that shared political information from February 1, 2022, to August 31, 2022. Data was collected using Crowd Tangle and public input through a social media poll. This resulted in the identification of eight popular Facebook pages, including both verified and non-verified ones. Notably, the "Ratta" page was recommended by many people as the most active in sharing political hashtags and was selected for further analysis.

Table 7: List of identified Facebook pages abstracted via Crowd Tangle

Page Name	Total interaction s	Interactio n Rate	Views on owne d video s	Page Follower s	Growth %
NewsFirst.L K	31.05M	0.064%	121.92	499.70M	+20.36%
Ada Derena Sinhala	14.48M	0.078%	61.32	225.84M	+10.84%
Ratta	7.90M	3.611%	1.57	33.45M	+32.33%
Azzaam Ameen	7.13M	0.581%	17.74	5.17M	+19.35%
Ceylon Ideas	1.37M	21.352%	0.59	10.95M	+1224.88 %

The Sri GAGs	1.30M	0.934%	2.36	1.33M	+6.03%
Aragalaya FM	1.09M	1.46%	5.34	7.23M	
Xposure News Media	461,660	2.177%	5.74	5.18M	

To address the second research question, in-depth interviews with an expert in the field were conducted to identify prominent hashtags on Facebook during the political unrest in Sri Lanka from February to August 2022. Around 14 hashtags were identified, with #GoHomeGota2022 being the most widely used, amassing 8,968,665 interactions and 85,583 posts. #gohomerajapaksas followed with 1.2 million interactions and 13,000 posts. #gohomegota and #gotagogama were the next most popular hashtags with 900,000 interactions and 9,000 posts, and 500,000 interactions and 1,300 posts, respectively. These hashtags played a significant role in shaping online discussions and capturing public sentiment during the political unrest, offering insights into the dynamics of political discourse on social media platforms.

For the third research question, data analysis using SNA approach was performed on the highly interacted hashtag, #GoHomeGota2022.

Figure 3:network diagram generated through Gephi representing interactions of #GoHomeGota2022 in Ratta page

The above diagram which is generated through Yifan Hu Algorithm illustrates a network graph of the posts from Ratta page which were reshared among other Facebook pages and groups, with the hashtag #GoHomeGota2022. Dots are the nodes which represent entity and edges are the relationship between entity. The different colored groups in the above diagram represents different data clusters which are clustered through modularity clustering. Each of them is connected with each other. For example, the purple cluster is connected with other smaller purple nodes as well as to the green cluster. Likewise, each and every data clusters are related to each and each and every node in clusters leading to spread of information.

Figure 4:Nodes of the network diagram of #GoHomeGota2022 hashtag interactions from Ratta page

In this diagram, the larger nodes, represent highest interactions in terms of shares. Therefore, in this case, the page/group GoHomeGota2022 has been highly involved in resharing posts. So, such nodes are considered as influential nodes as they have high interactions which leads to larger public reach when a post is shared. Similarly, betweenness centrality and closeness centrality measures were also used for the research.

In the diagram, the larger and more grey-colored nodes represent pages, groups, and links that have high betweenness centrality. These nodes play a crucial role in connecting different parts of the network and acting as intermediaries for information exchange. They have a significant impact on the flow of information and can potentially influence the spread of messages or ideas within the network.

Figure 7: Closeness centrality

Closeness centrality is a measure that quantifies how quickly and efficiently information or influence can spread from one node to other nodes in a network. In the diagram, the nodes that are positioned closer to each other indicate higher closeness centrality. These nodes are more central in the network and can easily reach other nodes with fewer intermediate steps or

connections. They have a shorter average distance to other nodes, allowing for efficient communication and information flow.

Section 4: Conclusion

In summary, the study focused on the spread of false information via hashtags on Facebook. It found that the "Ratta" page was a central hub for disseminating political information using hashtags. Notably, #GoHomeGota2022 was the most widely interacted hashtag during the study period.

The research highlighted the importance of educating users about the impact of hashtag-driven information spread and the need for effective platform moderation. This research further elaborates on how an information posted with a hashtag is reached to a larger audience and the impact that it could create. This also highlights that collaboration among researchers and social media platforms is essential to combat misinformation. This research provides valuable insights into the dynamics of information dissemination on Facebook and its implications for addressing misinformation.

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